

BR 7			BR 8		
FM-1	FM7		FM-1	FM7	

zt 0
-10min
zt 8

BR 9			BR 10		
FM-1	FM7		FM-1	FM7	

zt 0
-10min
zt 8

l-cry^{-/-}

L-CRY

β -ACTIN

Supplementary Data Figure 7 part 3